

Review of possibilities of correlating soil physical and chemical variables

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ABSTRACT

Apart from being a heterogeneous and dynamic system, soil complexity rises from the connections and interdependencies between its attributes. The correlation of soil properties can be employed to denote the association between quantitative variables and determine the extent and the way they are related. Furthermore, the correlations may disclose the predictive relationships of interest. The survey of the literature was made to summarize mathematical and statistical tools used for the analysis of the association between physical and chemical parameters of the soil. In line with the specific goals of COST Action SAGA, particular attention was paid to the available correlation of data relevant for archeological sites. The selected soil parameters and the methods used for the description of their linear and more complex non-linear relationships are outlined. The correlation of soil properties has been employed with much broader goals and objectives in other sub-disciplines of soil science, such as to analyze, explain, estimate, and predict different characteristics and processes. Some of these studies are reviewed to illustrate the methods of correlation that may be of interest in the archeological context.

1. Soil properties and their relations

Being a mixture of solid, liquid, gaseous components, and living organisms, soil represents a highly complex system. The solid phase approximately comprises 50% of the total soil volume and consists of both inorganic and organic compounds. Mineral matter (Dixon and Schulze, 2002), accounting for more than 95% of the solid phase, is usually separated into three particle-size fractions: clay (particle diameter < 0.002 mm), silt (0.002–0.05 mm), and sand (> 0.05 mm). The large surface area and the negative surface charge of the clay fraction particles result in their excellent adsorption properties and contribution in many chemical reactions in soils. The phyllosilicates and the oxides of iron, manganese, aluminum, and silicon belong to the clay-size fraction, whereas quartz, feldspar, mica, calcite, and gypsum are the components to the sand and silt fractions. Minerals are as well associated with soil physical properties (plastic or shrink-swell properties, compressive and shear strength, permeability to water and air, and aggregate stability), through interaction with soil water (Quirk, 1994).

Organic matter (OM) originates from natural plant, animal, and microbial biomass and inputs from human activities. Apart from living bio-mass, OM components span over simple organic molecules to complex polymers formed by the decomposition of plant and animal tissue (Stevenson, 1994). The high specific surface area and the high concentration and reactivity of surface functional groups of OM influence strongly on other soil properties, although the overall

content of OM in the soil is relatively low (usually < 5%). In particular, the humic and fulvic components exhibit a high affinity for the chelation of metal cations due to the presence of carboxyl (COOH) and phenolic (OH) groups. They also add to the pH-dependent negative charge of the soil, increasing the soil cation-exchange capacity.

The pore space of the solid soil phase is occupied by the liquid and gas phases, which relative proportion depends on environmental factors (Chesworth, 2008). Many organic and inorganic species (e.g., organic acids, carbohydrates, fulvic acids, and the ions of Ca, Mg, Na, K, Cl, SO₄, NO₃) may be dissolved in the soil liquid phase, and their actual concentrations largely depend on the solid-liquid partitioning equilibrium. Species within this phase are highly mobile and available for uptake by plants and microorganisms. With regard to the above-ground atmosphere, the important property of the gaseous phase in the soil is depleted O₂ concentration (elevated CO₂ concentration), due to the activity of soil microorganisms. Such an environment may result in a lowering of soil redox potential and has an impact on the chemical forms and solubility of multivalent species, such as Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ and Mn⁴⁺/Mn²⁺ (Sposito, 1989).

In addition to a range of abiotic constituents, soil provides habitat for living organisms (microflora and microfauna, mesoflora, macro and megafauna), and exhibits extreme biodiversity (Barrios, 2007). However, even though soil organisms largely influence ecosystem processes, the studies of the correlation between biological and physico-chemical soil features were outside of the scope of this review.

The physical and chemical properties of the soil that were used most often in the correlation studies are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Soil properties commonly integrated into correlation analysis

Soil properties	
Chemical	Physical
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pH • Cation exchange capacity • Electrical conductivity • Nutrient content • The concentration of macro and trace elements • Total organic carbon 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Texture • Density • Porosity • Water holding capacity • Resistance to penetration • Magnetic susceptibility

The elements found in the soil in total concentrations higher than 100 mg/kg are denoted as major (macro) elements (O, Si, Fe, Mg, K, Na, S, Ca, Mn, Fe, Al, C, Ti, etc.). In contrast, the trace elements are found in lower concentrations (<100 mg/g). In agriculture, the macronutrients are the elements that are demanded in relatively high levels (N, P, K, S, Ca, and Mg), while the micronutrients are the elements needed in trace amounts (Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, B, Mo, Cl, Ni (Ronon, 2007).

Soil pH is considered as a master parameter with either direct or indirect effects on soil chemical and biological processes (Bünemann et al., 2018). It is defined as the negative logarithm

of the concentration of the hydrogen ions, measured in the soil suspension in water (active acidity) or an aqueous solution of salt (KCl or CaCl₂) (exchangeable acidity). The mineralogical composition and the weathering highly influence the soil pH values. In a wet climate, soils are generally more acidic due to a higher precipitation rate (Slessarev et al., 2016). Higher acidity of the soil is also frequently provoked by human activities, especially by industrial effluents and the application of fertilizers (Sposito, 2008). Acidic soils are often characterized by Ca, K, Mg, and P deficiency (Heil and Sposito, 1997), and elevated mobility of cationic species. Increased alkalinity is associated with decreased solubility of trace metals, which may lead to low availability of essential elements such as Cu, Fe, Mn, and Zn (Fageria and Nascente, 2014). The buffering capacity of the soil represents the soil's ability to resist the pH change under the influence of different chemical agents and processes. It is driven by the protonation/deprotonation of the functional groups on the surface of soil constituents (Wang et al., 2018), and dissolution-precipitation of mineral phases (carbonates in particular).

The cation exchange capacity (CEC) is a measure of the quantity of cations that can be retained on soil particle surfaces (cmol_c/kg, or equivalent unit meq/100g), largely influenced by the type and content of organic matter and clay components. Although the content of organic matter is smaller compared to clay content, the contribution of OM in soil CEC is high (Harada and Inoko, 1975).

The electric conductivity of the soil (EC) (mS/m) is a measure of soil salinity (Dellavalle, 1992), which reflects the content of soluble salts (chlorides, nitrates, ammonia, potassium, sodium, etc.). EC is in the relationship with soil mineralogy and texture, and it depends on climate (rain) as well.

Total organic carbon (TOC) (g/kg) represents the content of carbon associated with the organic matter. It is correlated with the amount of fulvic, humic acids, and other organic compounds in soil, and it is a major parameter indicating the soil quality. On the other hand, inorganic carbon (IC) refers to the dissolved carbon dioxide and carbonates found in soil. The amounts and types of carbonate salts influence soil pH and its buffer properties.

Soil texture is defined by the relative content (% units or kg/kg) of particles of various sizes (sand, silt, and clay) (NRCS Soils, 2018). Soil texture is related to soil mineralogy, it governs the physical and chemical properties of the soil, and it is of the fundamental importance for soil classification.

Soil density (kg/m³) is defined as a ratio of a dry soil sample mass and its volume (USDA, 2008). It is defined as a mean value, given that the soil is a heterogeneous medium. The average soil density is between 2600 kg/m³ and 2700 kg/m³, which is close to the density of quartz. The density of the organic matter is lower, whereas the density of minerals containing Fe, Pb, and other heavy elements is higher compared to the average value.

The volume of soil pores with respect to soil volume is defined as porosity. The porosity is therefore dimensionless and reported as a fraction or percent. According to the dimensions, the macro (>75 μm), meso (30-75 μm) and micropores (< 30 μm) can be distinguished (*Glossary of Soil Science Terms*, 2008).

Water retention is a parameter that refers to the soil's ability to hold the water. It is highly dependent on particle diameter, where smaller particles exhibit a higher ability to retain water molecules. Furthermore, the higher content of organic matter also referees to better water retention ability of the soil. The saturation of soil with water is defined as the water-holding capacity and represents the mass of water retained by the defined mass of dry soil (g/g).

The soil strength (N/m^2), or the resistance to penetration, is defined as the minimum stress necessary to cause its failure (Hillel, 1998). It can be correlated with soil specific surface and particle density.

The magnetic susceptibility is a dimensionless measure of magnetic properties of the material when it is exposed to the magnetic field, and it is defined as a ratio of material magnetization (A/m) and applied magnetic field strength (A/m) (Egli, 2009). The magnetic susceptibility is highly dependent on mineralogical composition, particularly the presence of magnetite and maghemite.

2. An outline of the methods used for the correlation of soil attributes

The specific methods used to describe the linear and more complex relationships between physical and chemical soil properties are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation methods used in soil studies

Correlation methods	
Bivariate plots	Linear association between two soil attributes
Pearson correlation	Linear association between two soil attributes
Multiple linear regression analysis	The relationship between one dependent variable and two or more independent variables
Cluster analysis (CA)	Classification of soil samples or soil properties into clusters (samples/properties are similar within one cluster but dissimilar to samples/properties in other clusters)
Analysis of variance (ANOVA)	Comparison of the group means of two or more soil properties by estimating their variance
Principal component analysis (PCA)	Analysis, classification, and reduction of the dimensionality of numerical datasets, by searching for a linear combination of initial soil variables that most contribute to the differentiation of the samples
Discriminant function analysis (DA)	Constructing a model for the prediction of group memberships that enables understanding of the relationship between the sets of selected soil properties and the observations
Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	Nonlinear statistical data processing tools for modeling the complex relationships between inputs and outputs. Due to a learning capability and adaptivity, ANNs are used in a wide variety of applications such as classification, mapping,

Correlation is a statistical method that establishes the association between quantitative variables and indicates the strength of the links. Several methods that measure the degree of correlation are in use to assess the extent to which variables covary, depend, or predict one another.

- **Bivariate plots.** Bivariate data sets composed of measurements or observations on two variables can have different types of structure. One of the basic tools for exploring such data sets, i.e., the forms and strengths of pair-wise relationships between variables, are bivariate plots. The bivariate analysis enables the hypothesis of relationship to be tested and the significance of that relationship (if any) to be determined (Siegel, 2012) (Peck, 2014). In a bivariate plot, each pair of variables is represented by a point in a Cartesian coordinate system. The smaller is the distance of the points from the line they follow, the stronger is the relationship between two variables. The bivariate plots also enable determination of the direction of the linear relationship, i.e., is it positive or negative.

- **Pearson correlation.** The Pearson correlation is a commonly used method for measuring the strength and direction of the linear association between two variables (Pearson, 1895). Given a pair of variables (X, Y), the Pearson correlation coefficient is defined as:

$$r_{X,Y} = \frac{\text{cov}(X,Y)}{\sigma_X \sigma_Y}$$

where *cov* is covariance and σ_X and σ_Y are standard deviations of X and Y, respectively.

The Pearson correlation coefficient can vary between -1 (total negative correlation) through 0 (no correlation) to 1 (total positive correlation).

There are some restrictions in using the Pearson correlation coefficient. It assumes a linear relationship between two variables. As it relies on means and standard deviation, it is sensitive to outliers. The value of the Pearson correlation coefficient is determined not only by the strength of the correlation between variables but is also influenced by sample size. This must be taken into account while choosing a correlation method.

- **Multiple linear regression analysis.** Multiple linear regression is a multivariate technique for determining the relationship between a single response variable and some combination of two or more predictor variables (Montgomery DC, Peck EA, 2001). In its simplest form, multiple regression relates one response variable Y to two predictor variables X_1 and X_2 as follows:

$$\hat{Y} = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2$$

where \hat{Y} is the value of the response predicted to lie on the best-fit regression plane, b_0 is the intercept defining the Y value when both X_1 and X_2 are equal to zero, and b_1 and b_2 are regression coefficients which quantify sensitivity of Y to change in X_1 , and X_2 , respectively.

The multiple linear regression analysis also enables the determination of the magnitude and significance of the relationship between response and predictor variables.

- **Analysis of variance.** The analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a statistical method used to compare the group means of two or more samples by estimating their variance (Deming and Morgan, 1993). The method has few assumptions: normality (a dependent variable(s) is taken from normally distributed population(s)), independence of the observations (no relationship between the observations in a group or between groups), variance homogeneity (the variance of data between groups should be identical), dependent variable(s) should be measured in such a way which enables dividing into increments, no significant outliers should exist.

The different types of ANOVA are in use depending on the purpose and the experimental design. A one-way ANOVA compares the variance in the means of two or more different groups considering one independent variable. A two-way ANOVA examines the effect of two independent variables on the dependent variable. The n -way ANOVA could also be used with n being a number of variables of interest.

The ANOVA is a hypothesis-based method: the null hypothesis is that there is no significant difference between groups, and the alternative one is that there is at least one significant difference among them. After selecting the data, these hypotheses must be tested using statistical tests (F-ratio with associated probability value, post-hoc tests, etc.).

- **Principal component analysis.** Principal component analysis (PCA) is a multivariate statistical technique used for analyzing, classifying, and reducing the dimensionality of numerical datasets. The basis of the method is the search for directions in the space along which the distance between the points (data) is greatest, i.e., the search for a linear combination of initial variables that most contribute to the differentiation of the samples (Breton, 2007) (Jolliffe I.T., 1986). By PCA, the information contained in the initial data matrix is projected onto a small number of latent variables (eigenvectors) called principal components. Namely, the PCA decomposes the data matrix \mathbf{X} (composed of I objects represented by J variables) to the matrix of scores \mathbf{T} , the matrix of loadings \mathbf{P} and matrix of residual errors \mathbf{E} , which dimensions are $I \times K$, $K \times J$ and $I \times J$, respectively, where K is a number of principal components: $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{TP} + \mathbf{E}$.

The matrix of loadings composed of several vectors (principal components) obtained as a linear combination of original variables contains information on variables. The matrix of scores contains information on objects described by their projections onto principal components. The first component contains most of the variation of the data. The second component is orthogonal to the first and covers most of the remaining variation etc. By this method, data dimensionality reduction is obtained by eliminating the less important components without any considerable information loss. The magnitude of each eigenvector is expressed by its own eigenvalue, which gives a measure of the variance related to that principal component. The number of significant components is estimated from the values of eigenvalues. The coordinates of the data in a new base (score plot) are usually used for classification of data clusters, while the contribution to each component of the variable (loading plot) gives information on the relative importance of the variable to each principal component and their mutual correlation.

- **Cluster analysis.** Cluster analysis (CA) is an unsupervised pattern recognition method used to classify objects or cases into subsets called clusters in such a way that objects are similar within one cluster but dissimilar to objects in other clusters.

The first step in this analysis is to determine the similarity between objects which could be done by selecting one of the common numerical measures (Breton, 2007):

- (1) correlation coefficient
- (2) Euclidean distance, where the distance between the samples k and l is defined as:

$$d_{kl} = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^J (x_{kj} - x_{lj})^2}$$

where j is a number of measurements and x_{kj} is the j th measurement on sample i .

- (3) Manhattan distance defined as:

$$d_{kl} = \sum_{j=1}^J |x_{kj} - x_{lj}|$$

When the similarity matrix is obtained, the next step is to link the objects. There are a number of clustering procedures which could be classified into the following categories (Han et al., 2012).

Partitioning methods, distance-based methods with exclusive cluster separation with each object belonging to one group;

- (1) Hierarchical methods, which hierarchically decompose the objects data set. They could be agglomerative (starting with the object as a separate group and merges the objects or groups until the top level of hierarchy) or divisive (starting with all objects in the same cluster and splitting it into smaller clusters);
- (2) Density-based methods, the cluster is growing as long as the density, i.e., the number of data points around it exceeds a certain threshold;
- (3) Grid-based methods, where clustering is performing on the grid structure.

The final step is the cluster evaluation process consisted of an assessment of the clustering tendency (nonrandom structure of the data), determination of the number of clusters in a data set, and the measurement of clustering quality by applying appropriate extrinsic or intrinsic method.

- **Discriminant analysis.** Discriminant analysis (DA) is a multivariate analysis method used for separating objects into classes. The method provides discriminant functions which number is equal to the number of classes minus one. The goal of the DA is to construct a model that can be used for the prediction of group memberships. This model enables understanding of the relationship between the sets of selected variables and the observations and also the assessment of the variables contribution.

Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) is a simple parametric, mathematically robust method for feature reduction with discriminating character (Ziegel et al., 1998) It aims to find optimal discriminant features by maximizing the ratio of the between-class distance compared to the within-class distance of a given data set under supervised learning conditions. The features in the reduced space are linear combinations of the features in the original high dimensional space, where the coefficients of the linear combinations depend on the transformation matrix. This method enables the optimal transformation matrix to be found without the loss of information used for discrimination between classes. It uses Euclidean distance to classify unknown samples by computing linear functions $D_C = \sum_{j=1}^m v_j \bar{x}_{C,j}$ for each class (Ziegel et al., 2000), where v_j

represents the weights given to the variables which number is denoted by m , $\overline{x_{C,j}}$ is the mean variable j in class C . For an unknown sample u with variable values $x_{u,j}$ this function is calculated as: $D_C = \sum_{j=1}^m v_j \overline{x_{C,j}}$. The application of LDA is restricted to datasets in which the dimension of the data does not exceed the sample size. Because of this requirement, LDA is often preceded by PCA.

Quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA) is not much different from LDA except the assumption that the covariance matrix could differ among classes. When applying this method, the covariance matrix must be estimated for each class separately; this could be a problem in cases with many classes and not so many sample points.

- **Artificial Neural Network.** Artificial neural network (ANN) is a mathematical model consisting of many simple, highly interconnected processing elements (neurons) that simulate the human nervous system. There is always one input and one output layer and there should be at least one hidden layer, which enables ANNs to describe non-linear systems.

Numerous models of ANNs with different approaches both in architecture and in learning algorithms are in use. According to architecture, i.e., the manner in which the neurons of a network are structured, three main classes of networks could be identified: (1) single-layer feedforward networks, with input layer of source nodes projected directly onto an output layer of computation neurons (not vice versa), (2) multi-layer feedforward networks, with one or more hidden neurons used for internal interpretation of data from working environment and (3) recurrent neural networks, with at least one feedback loop which increases network learning capability and its performance.

The most important characteristic of the neural network is its learning capability which is performed by different procedures: supervised procedure (the knowledge on the working environment is presented to the network by a set of input-output examples), reinforcement procedure (input-output mapping by continued interaction with the working environment) and unsupervised procedure (no external overseeing of the learning process).

A number of algorithms are developed for training neural networks. One of the most frequently used is the algorithm with back-propagation in which the training process occurs in two phases: feed-forward and back-propagation (Rumelhart D., 1986). In the feed-forward phase, the input layer neurons pass the input values on the hidden layer. Each of the hidden layer neurons computes the weighted sum of its inputs, passes the sum through its activation function and presents the activation value to the output layer. After the computation of the weighted sum of each neuron in the output layer, the sum is passed through its activation function, resulting in one output value for the network. In the back-propagation phase, the error between the network output and the desired output values is calculated using the so-called generalized delta rule and weights between neurons are updated from the output layer to the input layer. The training process is successfully completed when the iterative process has converged. To increase the convergence rate of back-propagation networks, a number of different algorithms are developed such as delta-bar-delta, resilient propagation and quick propagation.

In contrast with back-propagation networks trained for evaluation of responses for each input object, networks with Kohonen algorithm are trained to provide the spatial location of an output neuron in a topographic map according to information extracted from input data (Kohonen, 1984). This location is determined by the most excited neuron in the network. Very similar to Kohonen algorithm is a counter-propagation algorithm. It is actually a Kohonen algorithm with

an additional layer of neurons below the Kohonen layer, which enables the use in solving supervised problems.

Due to their massive parallel structure, adaptivity, ability to provide continuous input or output data and possibility to be applied to complex systems, ANNs are currently used in a wide variety of applications such as classification, mapping, and modeling.

3. Review of studies of the correlation between physical and chemical properties of archeological soil

The signatures of human habitation and occupation may be represented by the physical and chemical properties of archeological soils. Given that past anthropogenic activities (e.g., fireplaces, food preparation, middening, craft-working) alter the natural sediments, multi-analytical methodologies have been employed to trace new soil characteristics and identify recognizable patterns. Elevated levels of Ca, P, Cu, Fe, Mg, K, Na, Zn, etc., have been commonly found in archaeological soils and associated with specific human inputs. Nevertheless, the association of past human activities with specific soil properties is often difficult due to the influence of other factors ([Simniškytė-Strimaitienė et al., 2017](#)).

The comprehensive sets of physical and chemical soil parameters were evaluated and discussed in several studies, without utilizing mathematical and statistical methods for data correlation ([Corrêa et al., 2011](#); [Cuenca-García, 2019](#)). A combined approach to understand the proxy responses of known archaeological features was tested in the recent work of ([Cuenca-García, 2019](#)). Geophysical and geochemical soil characterization was performed to detect archaeological features in three survey environments in Scotland. Over archaeological targets, a range of geophysical techniques (earth resistance, magnetometry, frequency domain electromagnetics (FDEM) and ground-penetrating radar (GPR)) was employed, and the obtained results were considered with respect to the results of other soil analyses (total phosphate, multi-element analysis, texture, pH, conductivity, organic matter content, magnetic susceptibility from archaeological deposits, topsoil and subsoil samples). Multiple conclusions have been drawn from this approach on how soil composition and processes may improve the understanding of the reasons behind geophysical data and maximize the detection of subsurface features.

For an enhanced interpretation of the results, the correlation of archeological soil attributes using mathematical and statistical methods was employed ([Table 3](#)). Depending on the specific goals, different variables and methods of correlation were employed. It can be observed from [Table 3](#) that the soil chemical parameters, particularly element concentrations, were most frequently used in correlation analyses. This is reasonable given that the activity area analysis of archaeological soils using multi-element characterizations represents a common practice.

Table 3. The correlation analyses applied to archeological soils

Number of soil samples	Correlating variables	Method of correlation	Aim of the study	Ref.
64–153 samples per house plan for ICP data, 20–35 samples per house plan for XRF data, 10 off-site samples per house plan	Concentration of Al, Ca, P, Cu, Zn, K and Mg) determined by ICP-OES and by XRF	Bivariate plots	To assess the effects of site lithology on the geochemical signatures of human occupation	(Oonk et al., 2009b)
Total of 88 points, samples collected from the 0.00-0.05, 0.05-0.10, 0.10-0.20, and 0.20-0.30 m depth layers.	Soil resistance to penetration, bulk density, macroporosity, microporosity, total porosity, geometric mean diameter, organic carbon.	Pearson correlation	To assess the spatial variability of soil properties and the impact of soil management and the current use	(Silva et al., 2016)
More than 50 soil samples from four stratigraphic units. Bulk samples of sediment were collected from each excavation unit.	Concentration of P, C and soluble salts, pH, χ_{rf} -initial reversible low frequency mass susceptibility and χ_{fd} -coefficient of frequency dependency, the number of artefacts	Pearson correlation	To connect the attributes of human site use with the changes in phosphorus and carbon concentrations in sediments and magnetic susceptibility of sediments, in combination with analysis of stone artefacts and faunal remains	(Marwick, 2005)
Not available	Chemical (pH, potential acidity, exchangeable cations, and soil organic carbon) and physical (particle size distribution, particles density, water retention, total porosity, microporosity, macroporosity, and bulk density)	Analysis of variance Pearson correlation	To characterize the chemical and physical properties of the top layer of two ADE profiles in a Gleysol and compare them with an adjacent soil	(Souza et al., 2016)

Table 3. Continued

Number of soil samples	Correlating variables	Method of correlation	Aim of the study	Ref.
Ethnoarchaeological samples (64), archaeological samples from two sites (146 and 60)	Concentrations of Al, Ba, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, P, Sr, Ti, and Zn	Linear correlation analysis Non-hierarchical cluster analysis (K-means)	To develop techniques for the identification and interpretation of activity areas in archaeological structures and to determine which elements serve to distinguish activities	(Middleton and Price, 1996),
148 topsoil samples (A horizon, and humose Ah horizon)	Concentration of 34 elements	Cluster analysis	To identify soil properties modified by human activity, to differentiate the areas affected by human and by arable cultivation	(Entwistle, J. A; Abrahams, P.W.; Dodgshon, 2000)
43 bulk soil samples, (with artefacts (7) , holding no artefacts (12), 25–40 cm depth (8) , 40–80 cm depth (16)	16 chemical elements, magnetic susceptibility, soil organic matter, inorganic carbon, pH values	Cluster analysis Principal component analysis	To determine possible anthropogenic indicators at the investigated locality	(Simniškytė-Strimaitienė et al., 2017)
Overall of 235 samples from 3 different fish processing areas	Concentrations of Al, Ba, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, P, Sr, Ti and Zn	Analysis of variance Cluster analysis	To identify and interpret subsistence activities in the archaeological record	(Knudson and Frink, 2010)
A total of 530 samples were collected and analysed: inside and outside of the plaza (388), across the surface of the plaza (74), from the lime-plastered playing surface of the ballcourt (21), from the plastered patio surfaces (47)	The concentrations of Al, Ba, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Na, P, Sr, Zn, Mn, and Ti	Linear correlation Principal component analysis Discriminant analysis	To reconstruct activity patterns using soil chemistry	(Wells, 2004)

The application of bivariate plots in the assessment of archeological soils can be found in the work of (Oonk et al., 2009). The multi-element soil analyses of grid samples from 3 archaeological house plans in the Netherlands (embedded in sandy clays, clays, and sands) were applied to assess the effects of site lithology on geochemical signatures of human occupation. The X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) and inductively coupled plasma optical emission (ICP-OES) spectroscopy of 1 M HCl extracts were used as two different experimental approaches for multi-element soil analyses. A data set was composed of ICP-OES data from the 3 grid sampled structures (64–153 samples per house plan) and XRF data from a selection of samples (20–35 samples from front and end regions of each house plan). Ten samples per house plan were also randomly collected of-site. The effects of site lithology on the geochemical signatures of human occupation were evaluated based on the bivariate plots between Al and Ca, P, Cu, Zn, K, and Mg concentrations. The elements were selected with the aim to distinguish modern anthropogenic (P, Cu, and Zn), ancient anthropogenic (Ca, P, Cu, Zn, K, and Mg), biogenic (Ca), and mineralogical (K, Mg) soil processes. Furthermore, the total concentrations of the elements measured by XRF were used in evaluating general trends in on-site element distributions, while the ICP-OES data referring to easily extractable elements were used to highlight anthropogenic trends.

Figure 1. Example of data correlation using bivariate plots: the relationship between Al and selected elements concentrations determined by XRF (the diagonal lines represent the regional geochemical background, and the ellipses indicate sub-grouping in the data) (Oonk et al., 2009).

Furthermore, the bivariate element relationships between the XRF and ICP-OES data were examined in order to specify groupings in the data sets. Each house plan was characterized by enhanced concentrations of different sets of elements. The off-site sampling, comparison to regional element background concentrations and the use of bivariate plots have helped to identify anthropogenic elements, element sources, and element distribution patterns. Soil enrichment with Cu, Cr, Sn, and Nd at all sites that have no or only a weak relation with lithology, as well as the depletion of Fe and Mn, were found to be universal indicators of human occupation. The construction of bivariate plots was particularly useful to verify background element levels and the nature of the selected elements and to assess element distribution patterns within house plans. These plots have revealed that the natural variation of most elements was lost due to the input of anthropogenic matter and subsequent soil processes. Most Al/element ratios of on- and off-site samples were different at the clayey sites, the opposite was found for the sandy site, whereas sub-grouping of on-site samples at the clayey sites provides the possibility of detecting features within house plans embedded in clayey lithologies. It was concluded that 1 M HCl extractable elements represent unreliable indicators of human occupation for clayey and calcareous clayey soils.

Pearson correlation, responsive to linear dependencies between variables, was implemented in the work of (Silva et al., 2016).

Table 4. Example of the identification of linear dependencies between soil properties using Pearson correlation. The data refer to different soil layers (Silva et al., 2016)

	RP	BD	Macro	Micro	TP	GMD	OC
0.00-0.05 m							
SRP	1.00	0.54*	-0.57*	0.20	-0.49*	0.04	-0.51
SBD		1.00	-0.66*	0.10	-0.79*	0.10	-0.63*
Macro			1.00	-0.57	-0.65*	-0.14	0.68*
Micro				1.00	0.25	0.08	0.02
TP					1.00	-0.09	0.61*
GMD						1.00	0.71*
OC							1.00
0.05-0.10 m							
SRP	1.00	0.53*	-0.54*	0.25	-0.55*	-0.01	-0.44*
SBD		1.00	-0.62*	-0.15	-0.68*	-0.04	-0.55*
Macro			1.00	-0.63	-0.52*	-0.01	0.49*
Micro				1.00	0.34	-0.03	0.26
TP					1.00	-0.04	0.55*
GMD						1.00	0.60*
OC							1.00
0.10-0.20 m							
SRP	1.00	0.43*	-0.49*	0.07	-0.49*	-0.15	-0.47*
SBD		1.00	-0.44*	0.10	-0.53*	-0.05	-0.51*
Macro			1.00	-0.59*	0.69*	-0.02	0.44*
Micro				1.00	0.17	-0.09	0.04
TP					1.00	-0.11	0.49*
GMD						1.00	0.51*
OC							1.00
0.20-0.30 m							
SRP	1.00	0.41*	-0.43*	-0.20	-0.44*	-0.05	-0.44*
SBD		1.00	-0.57*	-0.17	-0.82*	-0.21	-0.45*
Macro			1.00	-0.55*	0.68*	0.01	0.47*
Micro				1.00	0.23	0.18	0.05
TP					1.00	0.16	0.44*
GMD						1.00	0.56*
OC							1.00

* Pearson correlation, significant at 1 % probability by the t test. RP: soil resistance to penetration; BD: soil bulk density; Macro: macroporosity; Micro: microporosity; TP: Total porosity; GMD: geometric mean diameter; OC: organic carbon.

The spatial variability of soil properties was assessed in archeological Dark Earth Sites (Amazon region) under cacao cultivation, as it is believed that the soil management and the current use of the land may aggravate these changes. These sites stem from ancient Indian settlements and are characterized by the presence of ceramics and cultural artifacts, the dark color and large deposits of stable organic matter. A 42×88 m grid was established over the location, a total of 88 sampling points was selected and the blocks of soil samples with the undisturbed structure were collected at 0.00-0.05, 0.05-0.10, 0.10-0.20, and 0.20-0.30 m depth layers. Soil texture, aggregate stability, and organic carbon (OC) analyses were performed on disturbed soil samples, while the undisturbed samples were used to determine soil macroporosity (Macro), microporosity (Micro), total porosity (TP), and soil resistance to penetration (RP). The relationship between soil properties ($n= 352$) was calculated by Pearson correlation. In all soil layers, soil bulk density (BD) was in positive correlation with RP, while both variables had a negative correlation with OC. These findings indicate that both BD and RP decrease with the increase in the OC content. Furthermore, in different soil layers, a positive correlation between the geometric mean diameter (GMD) and OC was observed, showing the great importance of C in the aggregation of soil particles. Increased BD and RP values are correlated with the decrease in soil total porosity (TP) and with the increase in OC content. Based on the correlation analysis, the important role of organic carbon for the properties of the soil in the studied area was emphasized.

Another example of the linear data correlation can be found in the work of (Marwick, 2005). In this study, the characterization of archaeological sediments was used as a source of information on how humans lived at a site of Marillana A (inland Pilbara, Western Australia), which has evidence of prehistoric human occupation. The changes in phosphorus and carbon concentrations in sediments and magnetic susceptibility in combination with other sediment attributes were employed for the assessment of the frequency of visits and duration of stay on the investigated archeological site. Calculation of Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient for selected variables was performed and discussed. The chemical properties (concentration of P, C and soluble salts, pH) were correlated mutually and with the number of artefacts. The strong positive correlation was found between P and C concentrations and artefact density, implying that the increased discard of artefacts coincided with an increase in the intensity of site occupation. A moderate correlation between soluble salt concentration and artifact density, and a strong positive relationship between soluble salts and pH were also revealed. Quite the contrary, the correlations between sediment magnetic data (χ_{lf} - initial reversible low frequency mass susceptibility and χ_{fd} - coefficient of frequency dependency), the content of soluble salts, charcoal, and soil organic matter, was weak. This indicates that soil magnetic characteristics were not affected by human occupation and can probably be explained by simple increase in the frequency of site use, with no substantial changes in mobility or site function.

Chemical and physical properties of anthropogenic dark earth (ADE) soil from Bragança, Para (Eastern Amazon) were compared with the properties an adjacent soil (Souza et al., 2016). Soil samples were obtained from the topsoil layer of two areas from "Jabuti" archaeological site, and an adjacent no-anthropogenic area. Chemical (pH, potential acidity, exchangeable cations, and soil organic carbon) and physical (particle size distribution, particles density, water retention, total porosity, microporosity, macroporosity, and bulk density) properties were determined. The data for different locations were evaluated and compared using the ANOVA procedure, whereas Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to characterize the relationships between soil chemical and physical parameters. Both areas of ADE showed improved soil chemical properties compared to the adjacent soil, particularly in relation to phosphorus and calcium levels that

contributed to higher cation exchange capacity. The higher P levels were associated with the composition of the ceramics found in these areas. Furthermore, a strong positive linear correlation was found between the CEC and the organic carbon content. The quality of the organic matter actually had a greater effect on CEC than the quantity. Changes in soil physical properties were less noticeable comparing the samples from archeological and adjacent sites, but both areas of ADE exhibited higher water retention capacity.

In the study of (Middleton and Price, 1996), both the linear correlation and cluster analysis were implemented. The investigated localities encompassed one modern structure from Oaxaca (Mexico) and two archaeological house floors from British Columbia (Canada) and Oaxaca (Mexico), and the respective number of soil samples was 64, 146, and 60, for these tree sites. The main aim was to develop techniques for the identification and interpretation of activity areas in archaeological structures and to determine which elements serve to distinguish activities. The samples of soil collected from floors at studied sites were analyzed using ICP/AES in terms of Al, Ba, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, P, Sr, Ti, and Zn concentrations, following the extraction with 1N HCl. For each site, the linear correlation analysis was performed using the results of element concentrations. Based on correlation coefficients, the significant relationships between the elements were disclosed. The authors concluded that the strongest correlations could be best explained geochemically, while others are likely to occur due to human activity. Non-hierarchical cluster analysis (K-means) was found highly successful in separating the groups of elements, with high sensitivity to activities, functions, and construction. At the ethnoarchaeological site, for example, the groups of samples were separated using only the elements with the highest range of variation (Ca, K, Na, P, Sr, Ti, and Zn) and a five cluster solution. The differences between the clusters were explained by differential rates of elements incorporation and weathering between interior and exterior contexts.

(Entwistle et al., 2000) focused their study on the spatial variability of the soil parameters and discussed the applicability of multi-elemental analysis in providing information on individual occupation or habitation sites. One of the goals was to identify soil properties that had been modified by human activity and to differentiate the areas affected by human habitation from those influenced by arable cultivation of the adjacent field area. A random stratified sampling system was used over the archeological site at Greaulin (Isle of Skye), and topsoil samples were collected using the W traverse method. In total, 148 topsoil samples (A horizon, and humose Ah horizon) were collected using a systematic sampling grid, and by additional sampling within former buildings. For comparison, 30 control topsoil samples were collected off-site. The concentration of 34 elements was determined in the collected samples. Finally, the on-site geochemical data were expressed as “enrichment factors” relative to the mean value of the control (off-site) samples. The contour plots were constructed out of experimental data, to illustrate the trends in the soil properties. In order to group the elements with similar spatial enrichment patterns, cluster analysis (CA) was undertaken on the on-site soil geochemical data. Special attention was paid to the choice of similarity or distance measures. Multivariate statistical package MVSP was used, and Ward’s minimum variance method was undertaken on a squared Euclidean distance dissimilarity matrix. The data were converted to enrichment factors to standardize the data set. The four main patterns of spatial enrichment were identified based on the four main groups of elements identified by cluster analysis. The enrichment of the members of the groups and the sub-groups was discussed in detail in relation to human activities on the site. The authors have concluded that five elements (K, Rb, Th, Cs, and Sr) can be used in differentiating the areas that had been influenced by human habitation from those that had not. In comparison, P was a less reliable indicator of human habitation as its enrichment could possibly

be caused by other activities. Furthermore, the depth of the topsoil was found shallower and with higher levels of % loss on ignition in former habitation areas than in the former arable field areas. Enrichments of Ba (and to a lesser extent La, Ce, and Pr) occur both within the formerly inhabited areas and the former arable fields. It was also concluded that hot spots of enrichment in areas of human occupation, can be used for chemical finger-printing to locate possible sites of former settlement where no upstanding remains survive.

Figure 2. Example of the cluster analysis of the geochemical data: grouping of soil samples at Greaulin based on the concentrations of elements (Entwistle et al., 2000).

Several geochemical and geophysical techniques were used to describe the soil properties at an excavated heavily-disturbed Bėčionys hilltop settlement site in south-eastern Lithuania (Simniškytė-Strimaitienė et al., 2017) in order to determine possible anthropogenic indicators at this locality. In overall, 43 bulk soil samples were collected (19 pit-shaped features were bulk-sampled, and another 24 control samples were taken from the substratum level to determine the natural geochemical on-site background). The concentrations of major (Si, Al, Fe, Mg, Ca, Na, K, Mn, P, Ti) and trace elements (Cu, Rb, S, Sr, Zn, Zr) were measured. In addition, mass magnetic susceptibility, soil organic matter and inorganic carbon, and pH values were measured. Prior to multivariate analysis, these values were normalized by z-score transformation. The samples were regrouped on the basis of statistically interrelated variables using hierarchical clustering based on Euclidean distance. According to the dendrogram plot, four main groups of properties were identified and classified into: clay (Al, Fe, K, Na, Rb, Ti, and Sr), carbonates (Ca, Mg, SIC, pH), siliciclastic (Si, Zr), and biophilic group (elements P, Mn, Zn, magnetic susceptibility, accompanied by Cu, S and SOM). The biophilic group of soil properties was presumed to be an anthropogenic indicator; therefore, the distribution of their values in different sampling contexts was analyzed. Furthermore, the compositional variation for pit-shaped

structures was analyzed using principal component analysis (PCA). A bivariate plot of the first two component scores was overlain by a vector plot containing variable loadings. This representation combines the information on which variables differentiate between sample clusters with information on the relationship between individual variables. Several sets of anthropogenic markers were disclosed by multivariate statistics. The anomalies in P, Mn, Zn and MS were explained as the burning of fuel, taking into account their spatial and functional links, while the unusual enhancement of Al, Fe, K, Na and Sr was ascribed to infill that contained more clay. On the other hand, the local enrichments in Ca and Mg, accompanied by high pH and SIC, were explained by the calcareous geology. Finally, no correlation was found between the presence/absence of artefacts and soil properties.

Figure 3. Example of a biplot of the scores and loadings: the first two PCA components for variables in the sunken features (underlined– features with artefacts) (Simniškytė-Strimaitienė et al., 2017).

The ethnoarchaeological soils at known fish processing areas in the contemporary community of Tununak on Nelson Island (western Alaska), was examined in terms of the chemical composition (Knudson and Frink, 2010), to determine if multi-element characterization facilitates the identification and interpretation of subsistence activities in the archaeological record. A total of 235 soil samples were collected from three different fish processing areas. In addition, offsite soil samples from the locations that closely match the soils present at Tununak were collected using a statistically valid offsite sampling regime. After the extraction of soil samples (1 M HCl), the concentrations of Al, Ba, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, P, Sr, Ti, and Zn were determined using a quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (Q-ICP-MS). The elemental ratios Ba/Sr, Ba/Ca, and Sr/Ca were found depleted compared to the offsite area samples, most probably as the result of the incorporation of marine products into the fish processing area. In fish processing area samples, grouped by sample feature type, statistically significant elements were

analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The comparison of the mean elemental concentrations of the sample groups showed that the concentrations of Na, Mg, Al, P, K, Mn, Fe, Co, Cu, Pb were statistically different ($p < 0.05$) in each feature. Furthermore, the samples were analyzed using a four-solution cluster analysis that utilized the Ward's amalgamation method and a Euclidean distance measure. It was found that all these elements were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) for cluster group membership using an ANOVA means comparison. Based on the cluster analysis, the fish processing area features and the variability within and between the three fish processing areas were discussed.

In the work of Wells (Wells, 2004), the methods of linear data correlation, principal component analysis and discriminant function analysis were used to analyze the anthropogenic sediments from plaza spaces that no longer contain artefacts and neighboring trash deposits at the prehispanic site of El Coyote in northwestern Honduras. Multi-elemental characterization of a total of 530 soil samples was performed by ICP–AES analysis following weak acid-extraction, with the aim to reconstruct activity patterns using soil chemistry. The concentrations of Al, Ba, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Na, P, Sr, Zn, Mn, and Ti, were examined in the soil samples along with associated inventories of midden materials. In addition to P, the concentrations of K (contributed to soils by wood ash from cooking) and Ca (contributed by the use of lime in processing corn) were anticipated as useful for locating various activities. However, as the distribution of Ca deposited by cooking and food/beverage consumption was masked due to the composition of the plaza floor (crushed limestone), the distribution of K was used as a proxy for food preparation involving wood burning. The increased levels of P and the highest concentrations of K were found around the central plaza platforms. The levels of Ca, Fe, K, Na, P and Ti were used to differentiate middens surrounding the main plaza according to the activities accountable for their formation, given that the selected elements can be linked to specific human activities. Using a principal component analysis, two main compositional groups that derive from soils sampled in the main plaza and among the residential patios were identified. It was found that 97% of the sample variance can be explained by the first five principal components. The probabilities that the samples belong to one of the two reference groups were evaluated using a discriminant analysis, and the data were resolved into two primary compositional groups according to their origin (the main plaza or the residential patios). According to their provenances, 200 of 224 samples were correctly assigned by the first two discriminant scores.

Furthermore, the principal components analysis was performed using the chemical composition of the soil samples from all middens and suspected activity areas outside the plaza. These data were projected against the data obtained for the reference groups, in order to determine whether middens and activity areas could be correlated with plaza or residential spaces. The chemical group distinction was revealed: Group I - soils from middens and activity areas associated with craft production, Group II - soils from middens and activity areas in part created by ritual behavior, and Group III- soils from middens and activity areas consistent with domestic practices.

Finally, the linear correlation was used to analyze the relationships between the concentrations of soil elements and densities of artefact classes from the middens. In this way, a strong positive correlation between ceramic density and soil P was revealed; groundstone density correlates with K, suggesting that P and K are good indicators of food consumption and preparation. On the other hand, faunal remains such as bone and shell were in positive correlations with Na and Ca, indicating that increased Na and Ca concentrations in the soil may mark locations of food deposition. The moderate positive correlation between obsidian density and elements such as Ti,

Fe, and K, suggesting that the distribution patterns of these elements may reveal areas of lithic tool use and/or lithic manufacture.

4. Examples of the correlation of soil physical and chemical properties in various sub-disciplines of soil science

In various sub-disciplines of soil science, the correlation of soil physical and chemical attributes has been employed to analyze, explain, and predict various properties and processes, (such as to assess and improve the nutrient status, essential agrochemical, mechanical properties, and crop yield, to predict certain properties based on other known parameters, to investigate the processes of soil degradation, contamination, and rehabilitation, etc.). Due to the abundance of scientific results related to the correlation of soil properties, some examples are given below to illustrate the possibilities of different correlation techniques.

Linear correlation was often used to establish significant relationships between soil parameters. The association between soil properties (pH, OC, EC, and clay content) and available nutrient content (N, P, K, Ca, and Mg) was investigated using linear correlation analysis ([A. Bangroo et al., 2018](#)). Soil pH, OC, and clay content exhibited a strong effect on the availability of nutrients. The pH of soils showed a significant negative correlation with N and P, while the correlation of pH and available Ca and Mg was positive. The results were explained by increased volatilization loss of N, and increased precipitation of Ca and Mg phosphates with the rise in pH. The OC showed positive and significant correlation with available N and P, while a significant and positive correlation of clay content was detected with available K, Ca, and Mg. The results were found significant for the proper management of soil fertility.

Aggregate size distribution and stability are the indicators of soil conservation and productivity. The relationships between aggregate stability and soil physico-chemical properties were established by linear correlation ([Aziz and Karim, 2016](#)). A mean-weight-diameter (MWD) value was determined on five soils. The relationship between aggregate stability and organic matter was found highly significant. Aggregates 0.75 - 0.125 mm were positively correlated to fine, very fine sand and silt fractions and to organic matter, while the stability of aggregates showed a positive correlation with the content of clay, organic matter, and carbonate content.

The linear (Pearson) correlation analysis was also applied for disclosing associations of specific activities of radionuclides with fine-grained soil fractions, to provide insight into the key factors that affect radionuclide migration in the soil ([Dragović et al., 2012](#)). The specific activities of natural and Chernobyl-derived (^{137}Cs) radionuclides were determined in soil profiles of different soil types (chernozems, fluvisols, humic gleysols, eutric cambisols, vertisols, and gleyic fluvisols), typical for Belgrade (Serbia). The specific activity of ^{137}Cs was in a positive correlation with both the content of organic matter and the cation exchange capacity. In addition, the specific activity of ^{137}Cs was positively correlated with saturated hydraulic conductivity and specific electrical conductivity. On the other hand, strong positive correlations were found between ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th specific activities and Fe and Mn, indicating an association of these natural radionuclides with Fe and Mn oxides.

Correlation analysis is particularly interesting as a tool for the estimation of a certain hard-to-measure property, based on other properties. For example, CEC is a crucial chemical property that significantly affects soil quality, and it is an input parameter of many models being applied in agriculture and soil science. As the determination of soil CEC is time-consuming and laborious, developing a model for CEC estimation from other soil properties is essential. The relations

between CEC (dependent variable) and sand, silt, clay, organic matter contents, and pH (independent variables) was studied using 464 soil samples from A, B, and C horizons of different soils (Nourbakhsh et al., 2003). The results of linear correlation revealed that CEC is negatively correlated with sand fraction, while positively correlated with OM, clay, and silt fractions. Using stepwise regression analysis, it was confirmed that both OM and clay enter the model and that coefficients of determination (R^2) for the multiple models are higher than those of simple linear correlations. It was also found that the CEC of organic matter differs in different horizons. Based on the correlation study, it was concluded that in acidic soils, the contribution of OM in CEC is much higher than that of clays.

Another research predicted CEC, as well as water holding capacity (SWHC), by pedotransfer models developed from basic soil properties (sand, clay, pH, SOC) (Olorunfemi et al., 2016). The models were developed using statistical software and verified by comparing the relationship between measured and estimated CEC and SWHC of a total of 105 soil samples. Five linear regression models for predicting soil CEC, seven linear regression models for predicting SWHC were proposed, and the most acceptable models were selected.

A linear correlation was extensively used for establishing relationships between soil properties and the retention of various pollutants, but also for assessing their association with different soil fractions, which is the important information concerning environmental and health risks, and the selection of the appropriate remediation method.

Sorption and distribution of man-made radionuclide ^{90}Sr were investigated in different soil types (Rendzic Leptosols, Humic Fluvisol, Eutric Cambisol, Leptosol, Fluvisol, Dystric Cambisol, Mollic Leptosol, and Stagnosol) (Smičiklas et al., 2015). The correlation analysis (CA) has revealed positive correlations between soil pH, the content of clay and Ca/Sr ion-exchange ratio, and also between cation exchange capacity (CEC) and soil maximum sorption capacity for Sr. Besides, soil pH, CEC and TOC were statistically correlated with Sr mobility in the soil. Soil pH was negatively correlated with Sr content in exchangeable phase, whereas positively with the abundance of Sr in carbonate and Fe,Mn-oxide fractions. Increased TOC has influenced increased Sr content in carbonate fraction, whereas increased CEC provoked the decrease in water-soluble fraction. Using the same set of soil samples, the maximum sorption capacities of Co ions were found highly and positively correlated only with soil pH (Jović et al., 2017), whereas affinity and capacity for Cd accumulation were positively correlated with both soil pH and the CEC (Marković et al., 2019). Regardless of the aging time and Co concentration in the soil, soil pH and Co distribution were correlated. The pH was negatively correlated with Co(II) in the water-soluble and ion-exchangeable fractions, while positively correlated with the Co amounts in carbonate, oxide and organic fractions (Jović et al., 2017). Soil pH and the content of carbonate were significant factors of Cd stability in the soil, showing a negative correlation with exchangeable Cd content, and/or positive correlation with Cd distribution in other fractions.

Bivariate correlation analysis and path analysis were used for investigating the effects of soil characteristics on dinoseb adsorption (Guan et al., 2013). Overall, 55 samples of disturbed soil were included in the analysis. A stepwise regression analysis enabled the exclusion of the factors which had little influence on the adsorption. The organic carbon and clay contents were the most significant factors which affect the dinoseb adsorption, and therefore selected and used to establish the regression equation.

The changes in soil physical and chemical properties as affected by degradation can also be assessed using the correlation analysis (Xie et al., 2018). Different soil properties were tested considering lightly, moderately, severely degraded, and non-degraded alpine meadow. The exceptionally high positive correlation was found between soil organic carbon and total nitrogen,

total phosphorus, soil water. Furthermore, an extremely significant positive relationship between the pH and the soil bulk density was found, while soil pH and soil water were in a significant negative relationship. From the obtained results, it was concluded that only soil physical properties were affected by soil degradation, but also the chemical properties indirectly.

The multivariate analysis methods are also widely applied, particularly the PCA and cluster analysis.

The PCA was, for instance, used for the prediction of soil permeability. Collecting reliable soil permeability data is rather time-consuming and costly. Besides, the empirical equations for predicting permeability may be site-specific. Therefore, PCA was applied to 16 parameters analyzed from 37 sites consist of 91 samples to identify soil parameters that correspond strongly to soil permeability (Yulianti et al., 2018). The results of the study indicated five variables that have a strong correlation with soil permeability (water content, bulk density, particle density, porosity, and soil water retention), allowing construction of the preliminary permeability model, which has potential for further development.

A recent study showed that soil salinity and sodicity could be rapidly and efficiently monitored in risk areas using electromagnetic conductivity imaging (EMI) (Paz et al., 2020). EMI methods and inversion techniques were used to gain electromagnetic conductivity images of the true soil electrical conductivity (σ), and the potentials to predict both soil salinity and sodicity with these methods were investigated. The data collected with an EMI instrument at two modes and heights, and an inversion algorithm, were used to obtain σ . Soil samples from five layers to a depth of 1.35 m (along the EMI transects) were analyzed for the electrical conductivity of the soil saturation paste extract (EC_e), sodium adsorption ratio (SAR), pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC), exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP), volumetric water content (θ), and particle size distribution. Analysis of the correlation between σ and the soil properties was performed using the PCA. The correlations between σ and EC_e , ESP, and SAR were established, and the predicted results were evaluated using the leave-one-out cross validation method and calculating the root mean square error of prediction (RMSEP). The EC_e , SAR, and ESP were successfully predicted from σ , and it was found possible to classify the soil according to salinity and sodicity.

The soil hydraulic conductivity is an essential property for the wastewater infiltration rate into the soil subsurface. In the study of (Ganiyu et al., 2020), saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_{sat}) of soil around septic tank systems was estimated from the selected soil parameters. The soil water content, porosity, organic carbon, pH, bulk density, soil resistivity, and saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_{sat}) were determined in twelve soil samples. A multiple linear regression analysis was used to predict K_{sat} , and as a result, a new empirical linear equation was established for estimating K_{sat} from the selected parameters. Furthermore, three major factors accounting for 92.7% of the total variation in the soil hydraulic variables were identified by PCA, whereas the Cluster Analysis (CA) showed groups based on the correlation between hydraulic parameters and topographic settings.

The correlation of physical, chemical, and mineralogical attributes was performed to increase the collection of data for the sustainable use of Amazonian soils (Souza et al., 2018). The soil samples collected from 33 municipalities in the state of Pará, Brazil, were characterized in terms of particle size, fertility, silicon extracted by sodium hydroxide, Fe, Al, and Mn extracted by sulfuric acid, sodium citrate-bicarbonate-dithionite, and ammonium oxalate-oxalic acid. After descriptive analysis, multivariate PCA and cluster analysis were performed. The soil fertility was found low due to the low concentrations of bioavailable P, Ca, Mg, and K and had high concentrations of Al, Si, and Al oxide in the Cambisols. Both Cambisols and Nitosols exhibited higher concentrations of Fe and Mn oxides. An association between the organic carbon content

and pH, P, Ca, Mg, and K concentrations, was disclosed by the multivariate analysis. An additional association was also observed between clay, potential acidity, and the Fe and Al oxide concentrations. Based on the results, the adoption of agricultural techniques that maintain soil cover and include the addition of vegetable residues was proposed as a solution for increased agricultural yield.

The sustainability index approach (SI) based on the threshold levels of soil indicators and cumulative rating approach (CR) based on crop production limitations, can be used for the assessment of the sustainability of soil ecosystem in terms of soil degradation. To compare these two approaches, the research was conducted using 63 agriculture soil samples, and analyzing nine soil properties (pH, EC, SOC, particle-size distribution, available water holding capacity (AWHC), bulk density (BD), air capacity (AC), relative field capacity (RFC) and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) (Ghaemi et al., 2014). The PCA was used to select more effective indicators to conform to the minimum data set (MDS). A strong correlation between SI and CR was found. Six soil indicators selected as MDS (pH, SOC, AWC, BD, and SAR) were correlated significantly with SI and CR. PCA was found an appropriate method for selecting the more effective indicators to use fewer soil data input in assessing soil quality.

The impact of the operation of the largest coal-fired power plant in Serbia was investigated with regard to heavy metals in the soil (Ćujić et al., 2017). At sampling sites in the study area, the concentrations of Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni, Pb, V, and Zn were measured. The hierarchical cluster analysis has revealed a strong positive relationship between heavy metals and soil properties. The soil specific electrical conductivity (SEC), CEC, pH, carbonate content (CC), and sand were associated within one cluster. The second cluster, linking heavy metals, was split into two branches: Cr, Ni and Cu vs. Pb, Zn, Cd, and Mn, which enabled the discussion on their dominant substrates. Finally, the third cluster consisted of Fe, V, Co, clay, TOC, and silt. The Pearson correlation matrix of heavy metals and soil properties was also analyzed, and the strong correlations found among elements pointed to their common origin.

In addition to the linear correlation, PCA, and cluster analysis, the Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) found application in correlating soil attributes.

Different soil properties influence the distribution of elements in soil fractions, which in turn affects their mobility and the impact on ecosystems and biota. The chemical speciation of macro and micro elements (Al, Fe, Mn, K, Cd, Cr, Cu, Li, Ba, Ni, Pb, and Zn) in unpolluted soils of different types, were analyzed by sequential extraction procedure, and the effect of the physicochemical soil properties on the content, distribution, mobility, and availability of elements was investigated (Marković et al., 2016). PCA was applied to realize the relationship between the content of the elements and the soil fractions, as well as between the soil properties and the total content of the elements. Furthermore, the ANN model was developed to explore the applicability of the method in the prediction of the elemental distribution based on soil properties. For the development of the ANN model, the experimental results were arbitrarily divided into three groups (60% for training, 20% for cross-validation, and 20% for testing the network generalization capability). A multi-layer perceptron model (MLP) with input, hidden and output layer was used. The metal partitioning was dependent on both the metal and the soil type. Investigated elements, except Cd and Ba, were found in the less available fractions (F3, F4, and F5). Soil texture and TOC had a predominant impact on metal content and speciation. Samples with a higher percentage of sand exhibited increased contents of Pb, Zn, and Al in phase F1, which is readily accessible in the environment. The applicability of ANN was indicated by high accuracy of metal mobility prediction (particularly Al, Cd, Fe, K, Li, Mn, Pb, and Zn) in soils with a wide range of characteristics.

The ANN method was found capable of modeling and estimating the sorption coefficients of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) in relation to soil organic carbon (Shabani and Gholamalizadeh Ahangar, 2016). The modeling of sorption coefficients of important organic pollutants provides benefits compared to laborious and costly experimental measurements. Consequently, an artificial intelligence-based model was derived to predict soil sorption coefficients (K_{oc} and K_d) of phenanthrene, using minimum input data from the studies carried out on soil samples from an under pasture paddock (South Australia). The best performing model was chosen based on an eight-fold cross-validation technique. Multilayer perceptron (MLP) artificial neural network (ANN) model with a 1-6-1 structure explained 97% and 95% of K_d and K_{oc} variances, using soil organic carbon content as only input data.

ANN network model was developed to predict soil texture distributions (Zhao et al., 2009). Given that high-resolution soil maps are available for small areas, an ANN approach was applied with the aim of producing high-resolution soil maps in the area with similar conditions without additional field surveys. The sand, clay, and silt contents in the soil were predicted based on soil attributes obtained from coarse resolution soil maps in combination with hydrographic parameters derived from a digital elevation model (DEM). The hydrographic parameters included soil terrain factor, sediment delivery ratio, and vertical slope position. The experimentally assessed soil texture was used to train and test the ANN model. The Levenberg–Marquardt optimization algorithm provided better results than the training method based on the resilient back-propagation algorithm. The root mean square errors between model predictions and field determination were 4.0 for clay and 6.6 for sand contents. It has been shown that the trained ANN model can be used for interpolations in the areas where the model was calibrated, or other areas with a similar relative range of input parameters.

The prediction of soil hydraulic properties from routinely surveyed soil data is of a great significance given that the direct measurements of soil hydraulic properties are often expensive and time-consuming. In the study of (D’Emilio et al., 2018), the application of pedotransfer functions (PTFs) was carried out for 359 Sicilian soils by implementing five different artificial neural networks (ANNs) to estimate the parameter of the van Genuchten (vG) model for water retention curves. The ANN models were trained using the raw data for soil texture, bulk density (ρ_b), organic carbon content (OC), and porosity. The ability of ANNs to predict the vG parameters were evaluated on the basis of the normalized root-mean-square errors (NRMSE) and normalized mean absolute errors (NMAE), as well as their ability to predict the water retention data. The most efficient network was selected using the Akaike’s information criterion (AIC) test. Using four input parameters (clay, sand, and silt fractions, and OC), developed ANNs simulated soil water retention data with high prediction accuracy. Furthermore, the AIC efficiency criterion indicated that the most efficient ANN model was trained with a relatively low number of input nodes.

5. Concluding remarks

The review of the scientific literature was made to (i) identify the soil physical and chemical parameters used in correlation analyses, (ii) review the methods used in correlating soil physical and chemical attributes in various studies, (iii) illustrate different objectives of these studies and the aims achieved by the correlation analysis. Compared to the literature in various fields of soil science, it is noted that some of the correlation methods are as well used in the archaeological

context (linear correlation, multiple linear regression analysis, cluster analysis, analysis of variance, principal component analysis, and discriminant function analysis). On the other hand, the prospects of Artificial Neural Network (ANN) modeling have not yet been tested for correlating and predicting the properties of archeological soils. Furthermore, the analysis of the association of elements with different soil fractions (sequential extraction) is underutilized considering archeological specimens, whereas the correlation of element content in different soil fractions or the correlation of elements distribution with other soil properties has not been investigated so far. Although the research into archeological sites can be significantly enhanced utilizing the correlation analysis, the obstacles to more intensive use of such data interpretation include the substantial number of soil samples in combination with long duration and high cost of some analysis, particularly chemical. Accordingly, the sampling strategy must be designed in such a way that the crucial information is obtained through the optimal number of samples. Furthermore, the number and type of soil attributes must be carefully selected according to the aims of the study.

REFERENCES

- A. Bangroo, S., B. Dar, S., Itoo, H., Mubarak, T., R. Malik, A., 2018. Effect of Physico-Chemical Properties of Soil on Available Soil Nutrients in Apple Orchards of District Kulgam. *Curr. World Environ.* 13, 270–276. <https://doi.org/10.12944/CWE.13.2.12>
- Aziz, S.A., Karim, S.M., 2016. The Effect of Some Soil Physical and Chemical Properties on Soil Aggregate Stability in Different Locations in Sulaimani and Halabja Governorate. *Open J. Soil Sci.* 6, 81–88. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojss.2016.64009>
- Barrios, E., 2007. Soil biota, ecosystem services and land productivity. *Ecol. Econ.* 64, 269–285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2007.03.004>
- Brereton, R.G., 2007. *Applied Chemometrics for Scientists*. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd., Chichester, England.
- Bünemann, E.K., Bongiorno, G., Bai, Z., Creamer, R.E., De Deyn, G., de Goede, R., Fleskens, L., Geissen, V., Kuyper, T.W., Mäder, P., Pulleman, M., Sukkel, W., van Groenigen, J.W., Brussaard, L., 2018. Soil quality – A critical review. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 120, 105–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2018.01.030>
- Chesworth, W., 2008. *Encyclopedia of soil sciences*. Springer, Dordrecht, Netherlands.
- Corrêa, G.R., Schaefer, C.E.G., Freitas Melo, V. de, Souza, K.W. de, Ker, J.C., Rodrigues, I.M.M., Senra, E.O., 2011. Physical and chemical attributes of archeological soils developed from shell middens in the Região dos Lagos, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. *Rev. Bras. Ciência do Solo.* <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0100-06832011000400004>
- Cuenca-García, C., 2019. Soil geochemical methods in archaeo-geophysics: Exploring a combined approach at sites in Scotland. *Archaeol. Prospect.* 26, 57–72. <https://doi.org/10.1002/arp.1723>
- Ćujić, M., Dragović, S., Đorđević, M., Dragović, R., Gajić, B., 2017. Reprint of “Environmental assessment of heavy metals around the largest coal fired power plant in Serbia.” *CATENA* 148, 26–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2015.12.018>
- D’Emilio, A., Aiello, R., Consoli, S., Vanella, D., Iovino, M., 2018. Artificial Neural Networks

- for Predicting the Water Retention Curve of Sicilian Agricultural Soils. *Water* 10, 1431. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10101431>
- Dellavalle, N.B. (Ed.), 1992. Determination of specific conductance in supernatant 1:2 soil:water solution, in: *Handbook on Reference Methods for Soil Analysis*. Soil and Plant Analysis Council, Inc., Athens, GA, pp. 44–50.
- Deming, S.N., Morgan, S.L., 1993. *Experimental Design: A Chemometric Approach*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, Netherlands., Amsterdam.
- Dixon, J.B., Schulze, D.G. (Eds.), 2002. *Soil Mineralogy with Environmental Applications*. SSSA, Madison, WI. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssabookser7.frontmatter>
- Dragović, S., Gajić, B., Dragović, R., Janković-Mandić, L., Slavković-Beškoski, L., Mihailović, N., Momčilović, M., Čujić, M., 2012. Edaphic factors affecting the vertical distribution of radionuclides in the different soil types of Belgrade, Serbia. *J. Environ. Monit.* 14, 127–137. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1EM10457H>
- Egli, R., 2009. Magnetic susceptibility measurements as a function of temperature and frequency I: inversion theory. *Geophys. J. Int.* 177, 395–420. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-246X.2009.04081.x>
- Entwistle, J.A., Abrahams, P.W., Dodgshon, R.A., 2000. The Geoarchaeological Significance and Spatial Variability of a Range of Physical and Chemical Soil Properties from a Former Habitation Site, Isle of Skye. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 27, 287–303. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1006/jasc.1999.0453>
- Fageria, N.K., Nascente, A.S., 2014. Management of Soil Acidity of South American Soils for Sustainable Crop Production. *Adv. Agron.* 128, 221–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-802139-2.00006-8>
- Ganiyu, S.A., Rabiou, J.A., Olatoye, R.O., 2020. Predicting hydraulic conductivity around septic tank systems using soil physico-chemical properties and determination of principal soil factors by multivariate analysis. *J. King Saud Univ. - Sci.* 32, 555–562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2018.08.008>
- Ghaemi, M., Astarai, A., Emami, H., Nassiri Mahalati, M., Sanaeinejad, S., 2014. Determining soil indicators for soil sustainability assessment using principal component analysis of astan quds- east of mashhad- Iran. *J. soil Sci. plant Nutr.* 0–0. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-95162014005000077>
- Glossary of Soil Science Terms, 2008.
- Guan, Y., Wei, J., Zhang, D., Zu, M., Zhang, L., 2013. To Identify the Important Soil Properties Affecting Dinoseb Adsorption with Statistical Analysis. *Sci. World J.* 2013, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/362854>
- Han, J., Kamber, M., Pei, J., 2012. *Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques*, *Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2009-0-61819-5>
- Harada, Y., Inoko, A., 1975. Cation-exchange properties of soil organic matter. *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* 21, 361–369. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00380768.1975.10432651>
- Heil, D., Sposito, G., 1997. Chapter 3 Chemical attributes and processes affecting soil quality. *Dev. Soil Sci.* [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481\(97\)80030-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481(97)80030-X)
- Hillel, D. (Ed.), 1998. *Environmental Soil Physics*, First. ed. Academic Press.
- Jolliffe I.T., 1986. *Principal Component Analysis*. Springer, New York.
- Jović, M., Šljivić-Ivanović, M., Dimović, S., Marković, J., Smičiklas, I., 2017. Sorption and mobility of Co(II) in relation to soil properties. *Geoderma* 297, 38–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.03.006>
- Knudson, K.J., Frink, L., 2010. Ethnoarchaeological analysis of Arctic fish processing: chemical

- characterization of soils on Nelson Island, Alaska. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 37, 769–783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2009.11.007>
- Kohonen, T., 1984. *Self-Organization and Associative Memory*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- Marković, J., Jović, M., Smičiklas, I., Pezo, L., Šljivić-Ivanović, M., Onjia, A., Popović, A., 2016. Chemical speciation of metals in unpolluted soils of different types: Correlation with soil characteristics and an ANN modelling approach 165, 71–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2016.03.004>
- Marković, J., Jović, M., Smičiklas, I., Šljivić-Ivanović, M., Onjia, A., Trivunac, K., Popović, A., 2019. Cadmium retention and distribution in contaminated soil: effects and interactions of soil properties, contamination level, aging time and in situ immobilization agents. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.03.001>
- Marwick, B., 2005. Element concentrations and magnetic susceptibility of anthrosols: Indicators of prehistoric human occupation in the inland Pilbara, Western Australia. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 32, 1357–1368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2005.03.009>
- Middleton, W.D., Price, D.T., 1996. Identification of Activity Areas by Multi-element Characterization of Sediments from Modern and Archaeological House Floors Using Inductively Coupled Plasma-atomic Emission Spectroscopy. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 23, 673–687. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jasc.1996.0064>
- Montgomery DC, Peck EA, V.G., 2001. *Introduction to Linear Regression Analysis*, 3rd ed. ed. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Nourbakhsh, F., Jalalian, A., Shariatmadari, H., 2003. Estimation of Cation Exchange Capacity from Some Soil Physical and Chemical Properties. *J. Sci. Technol. Agric. Nat. Resour.* 7, 107–118.
- NRCS Soils, 2018. Soil Texture Calculator. United States Department of Agriculture. [WWW Document].
- Olorunfemi, I., Fasinmirin, J., Ojo, A., 2016. Modeling cation exchange capacity and soil water holding capacity from basic soil properties. *EURASIAN J. SOIL Sci.* 5, 266. <https://doi.org/10.18393/ejss.2016.4.266-274>
- Oonk, S., Slomp, C.P., Huisman, D.J., Vriend, S.P., 2009. Effects of site lithology on geochemical signatures of human occupation in archaeological house plans in the Netherlands. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 36, 1215–1228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2009.01.010>
- Paz, A.M., Castanheira, N., Farzaman, M., Paz, M.C., Gonçalves, M.C., Monteiro Santos, F.A., Triantafyllis, J., 2020. Prediction of soil salinity and sodicity using electromagnetic conductivity imaging. *Geoderma* 361, 114086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.114086>
- Pearson, K., 1895. Notes on Regression and Inheritance in the Case of Two Parents. *Proc. R. Soc. London* 58, 240–242.
- Peck, R., 2014. *Statistics: Learning from Data*. Brooks/Cole, Cengage Learning, IN, USA.
- Quirk, J., 1994. Interparticle forces: A basis for the interpretation of soil physical behavior, in: Sparks, D.L. (Ed.), . Orlando: Academic Press.
- Ronen, E., 2007. Micro elements in agriculture, The importance of microelements. *Pract. Hydroponics Greenhouses* 39–48.
- Rumelhart D., H.G.W.R., 1986. Learning internal representations by error propagation, in: Rumelhart, D., McClelland, J. (Ed.), *Distributed Parallel Processing: Explorations in the Microstructures of Cognition*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, USA.
- Shabani, A., Gholamalizadeh Ahangar, A., 2016. Predicting Soil Sorption Coefficients of Phenanthrene Using a Neural Network Model. *Heal. Scope* 5.

- <https://doi.org/10.17795/jhealthscope-29634>
- Siegel, A.F., 2012. *Practical Business Statistics*. Elsevier Inc., MA, USA.
- Silva, D.M.P. da, Campos, M.C.C., Franciscan, U., Alho, L.C., Santos, L.A.C. dos, Paula Neto, P. de, Bergamin, A.C., Souza, Z.M. de, 2016. Spatial Variability of Soil Properties in Archeological Dark Earth Sites under Cacao Cultivation. *Rev. Bras. Ciência do Solo* 40, e014081. <https://doi.org/10.1590/18069657rbcs20140816>
- Simniškytė-Strimaitienė, A., Selskienė, A., Vaičiūnienė, J., Pakštas, V., Šmigelskas, R., 2017. Tracing Archaeology through Geochemistry: an Example of a Disturbed Prehistoric Hilltop Settlement Site in South-Eastern Lithuania. *Interdiscip. Archaeol. - Nat. Sci. Archaeol.* VIII, 17–33. <https://doi.org/10.24916/iansa.2017.1.2>
- Slessarev, E.W., Lin, Y., Bingham, N.L., Johnson, J.E., Dai, Y., Schimel, J.P., Chadwick, O.A., 2016. Water balance creates a threshold in soil pH at the global scale. *Nature* 540, 567.
- Smičiklas, I., Jović, M., Šljivić-Ivanović, M., Mrvić, V., Čakmak, D., Dimović, S., 2015. Correlation of Sr 2 + retention and distribution with properties of different soil types. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.04.003>
- Souza, E.S. de, Fernandes, A.R., De Souza Braz, A.M., Oliveira, F.J. de, Alleoni, L.R.F., Campos, M.C.C., 2018. Physical, chemical, and mineralogical attributes of a representative group of soils from the eastern Amazon region in Brazil. *SOIL* 4, 195–212. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-4-195-2018>
- Souza, L.C. de, LIMA, H.V. de, RODRIGUES, S., KERN, D.C., SILVA, Á.P. da, PICCININ, J.L., 2016. Chemical and physical properties of an anthropogenic dark earth soil from Bragança, Para, Eastern Amazon. *Acta Amaz.* 46, 337–344. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-4392201505663>
- Sposito, G., 2008. *The Chemistry of Soils*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Sposito, G., 1989. *The Chemistry of Soils*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Stevenson, F.J., 1994. *Humus chemistry: genesis, composition, reactions*. Wiley, New York.
- USDA, 2008. *Soil Quality Indicators, Bulk density* [WWW Document].
- Wang, Y., Cheng, P., Li, F., Liu, T., Cheng, K., Yang, J., Lu, Y., 2018. Variable charges of a red soil from different depths: Acid-base buffer capacity and surface complexation model. *Appl. Clay Sci.* 159, 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CLAY.2017.08.003>
- Wells, E.C., 2004. Investigating Activity Patterns In Prehispanic Plazas: Weak Acid-Extraction ICP-AES Analysis of Anthrosols at Classic Period El Coyote, Northwestern Honduras. *Archaeometry* 46, 67–84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4754.2004.00144.x>
- Xie, H.H., Wu, Q.G., Hu, J.Y., Yu, L.F., Bie, P.F., Wang, H., Deng, D.Z., 2018. Changes in Soil Physical and Chemical Properties During the Process of Alpine Meadow Degradation along the Eastern Qinghai-Tibet Plateau. *Eurasian Soil Sci.* 51, 1440–1446. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1064229318130045>
- Yulianti, M., Sudriani, Y., Rustini, H.A., 2018. Preliminary study of soil permeability properties using principal component analysis. *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 118, 12029. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/118/1/012029>
- Zhao, Z., Chow, T.L., Rees, H.W., Yang, Q., Xing, Z., Meng, F.-R., 2009. Predict soil texture distributions using an artificial neural network model. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 65, 36–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2008.07.008>
- Ziegel, E.R., Massart, D., Vandeginote, B., Buydens, L., DeJong, S., Lewi, P., Smeyers-Verbeke, J., 1998. *Handbook of Chemometrics and Qualimetrics: Part A. Technometrics* 40, 264. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1271196>
- Ziegel, E.R., Massart, D.L., Vandeginste, B.G.M., Buydens, L.M.C., de Jong, S., Lewi, P.J.,

Verbeke, J.S., 2000. Handbook of Chemometrics and Qualimetrics, Part B. Technometrics 42, 218. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1271476>